

Effectiveness and Capability of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS): A Powerful Tool for Land use and Land Cover (LULC) Change and Accuracy Assessment

Land use and Land Cover (LULC) Change and Accuracy Evaluation using Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

¹Nitin Liladhar Rane

²Anand Achari

³Saurabh P. Choudhary

⁴Monica Giduturi

^{1,2,3,4}Vivekanand Education Society's College of Architecture (VESCOA), Mumbai, India

Abstract:- In this research paper, the effectiveness and capability of remote sensing (RS) and geographic information systems (GIS) are investigated as powerful tools for analyzing changes in land use and land cover (LULC), as well as for accuracy assessment. The study employs the literature of satellite imagery and GIS data to evaluate LULC changes over a period and to assess the accuracy of the analysis. Moreover, the research investigates the land use and land cover change detection analysis using RS and GIS, application of artificial intelligence (AI), and Machine Learning (ML) in LULC classification, environment and risk evaluation, stages of process LULC classification, factors affecting the LULC classification, accuracy assessment, and potential applications of RS and GIS in predicting future LULC changes and supporting decision-making processes. The findings of the study suggest that RS and GIS are highly effective and accurate for LULC analysis and assessment, with substantial potential for predicting and managing future changes in land use and land cover. The paper emphasizes the importance of utilizing RS and GIS techniques in the field of sustainable environmental management and resource planning.

Keywords:- Remote Sensing (RS); Geographic Information Systems (GIS); Land use and Land Cover (LULC); Accuracy Assessment; Scale; Resolution Effects.

I. INTRODUCTION

The understanding of land use and land cover (LULC) changes is of utmost importance, and the integration of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has revolutionized the study of these changes [1-4]. Land use denotes how humans use land, while land cover refers to the physical and biological features on the Earth's surface. The use of RS involves sensors aboard platforms such as satellites, drones, and aircraft to collect data from various spectral bands. This data provides information on

the type of land cover on the surface and can help understand changes in LULC. GIS, on the other hand, is a computer-based system used to capture, store, manipulate, analyze, and display geographically referenced data. It can be used to create detailed maps of land cover types and analyze patterns of land use.

The use of RS and GIS in LULC studies is crucial because it allows for the creation of detailed and accurate land cover maps that can be used to monitor changes over time [4-7]. These maps provide information on the extent and magnitude of LULC changes and help identify areas that need protection or management interventions. For example, it can help detect areas at risk of desertification or forest fires, enabling interventions to mitigate these risks.

The integration of RS and GIS has also allowed for the development of advanced modeling techniques, such as land use change models and spatially explicit simulation models, which can predict future LULC changes. This information can help simulate different scenarios, such as the impact of urbanization on natural areas or the effect of climate change on agricultural production. The data generated can inform decision-making and policy development, allowing for proactive management interventions to be put in place.

RS and GIS also play an essential role in understanding the impacts of LULC changes on the environment [8-10]. For instance, it can monitor changes in vegetation cover and detect changes in carbon storage, a crucial factor in climate change mitigation. It can also monitor changes in water resources, such as the impact of deforestation on water quality and availability.

The integration of RS and GIS is critical in understanding the dynamics of LULC changes. It helps create accurate land cover maps, advanced modeling techniques, and monitor the impacts of LULC changes on the environment [11-14]. The data generated can inform

decision-making and policy development, enabling effective land management, conservation, and policymaking. RS and GIS are powerful tools that can contribute to sustainable development, making them essential in today's world.

This paper examines the efficacy and potential of remote sensing (RS) and geographic information systems (GIS) as potent instruments for analyzing land use and land cover (LULC) changes and assessing accuracy. Remote sensing involves collecting information about the Earth's surface through sensors aboard various platforms, such as satellites, aircraft, or drones. GIS is a computer-based system that captures, stores, manipulates, analyzes, and presents geographically referenced data. Together, these tools have revolutionized the way we investigate and understand the Earth's surface and its changes over time.

Land use and land cover change is a significant challenge faced by many regions worldwide. Multiple factors drive it, including population growth, urbanization, deforestation, and agricultural expansion. It is crucial to comprehend the magnitude and drivers of these changes to enable effective land management, conservation, and policymaking.

Remote sensing and GIS offer a powerful approach for quantifying LULC changes over time. Researchers can evaluate changes in vegetation cover, urbanization, deforestation, and other LULC changes by comparing images of the same area taken at different times. Furthermore, these tools can provide spatially explicit data on the location and extent of these changes, facilitating more targeted and effective management interventions.

The accuracy and reliability of data provided by remote sensing and GIS are critical. Accuracy assessment involves evaluating the correctness and dependability of remote sensing and GIS data by comparing it with ground truth data. Ground truth data are obtained through field surveys or other dependable sources and provide a reference point for assessing the accuracy of remote sensing and GIS data.

This paper investigates the effectiveness and capability of remote sensing and GIS for LULC change and accuracy assessment. It aims to present a comprehensive review of the latest methods and techniques used for image processing, classification, and accuracy assessment in these areas. The strengths and limitations of remote sensing and GIS for LULC change analysis and accuracy assessment are discussed, and areas requiring further research are identified.

This paper underscores the importance of remote sensing and GIS as powerful tools for examining land use and land cover changes and assessing accuracy. The data generated by these tools can inform effective land management, conservation, and policymaking, making them indispensable for sustainable development.

II. LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGE DETECTION ANALYSIS USING RS AND GIS

Land use and land cover change (LULCC) is the process of altering natural and semi-natural landscapes through human activities such as urbanization, agriculture, mining, and forestry. LULCC analysis has become a crucial tool for environmental management and planning, as it provides valuable information about the effects of land use changes on ecological systems, biodiversity, and socio-economic development. Remote sensing (RS) and geographic information systems (GIS) are powerful technologies that allow for the detection, characterization, and quantification of LULCC using digital images and spatial data.

Detecting LULCC involves comparing land use and land cover maps derived from different time periods using RS data obtained from satellite, airborne, or ground-based sensors that capture information on the spectral, temporal, and spatial characteristics of the Earth's surface. Spectral information reflects the reflectance or emission of energy by different land cover types in various wavelength bands, while temporal information reflects seasonal and annual changes in land use patterns. Spatial information reflects the location and extent of land use and land cover features, which are represented as pixels in digital images.

GIS is used to manage and analyze spatial data, including RS data, to generate maps and other geospatial products. GIS integrates multiple data layers, such as topography, climate, soil, and land use, and creates complex models and simulations that assess the impacts of LULCC on various environmental and socio-economic variables. GIS identifies hotspots of LULCC, such as areas with high rates of deforestation or urbanization and prioritizes conservation and development interventions based on the ecological and social values of affected areas [15-17].

LULCC analysis using RS and GIS involves data acquisition, preprocessing, classification, accuracy assessment, and change detection [18,19]. Data acquisition involves selecting and obtaining RS and other spatial data relevant to the study area and research question. Preprocessing involves correcting, enhancing, and registering RS data for quality and compatibility with GIS analysis. Classification involves assigning land use and land cover classes to RS data pixels based on their spectral and contextual properties. Classification algorithms can be supervised or unsupervised and use various techniques, such as maximum likelihood, decision trees, and neural networks.

Accuracy assessment involves validating classification results using ground truth data collected in the field or from other sources, such as high-resolution imagery or historical maps. Change detection involves comparing land use and land cover maps derived from different time periods using post-classification comparison, image differencing, and object-based analysis. Change detection identifies areas where LULCC has occurred, quantifies the magnitude and

direction of LULCC, and evaluates the causes and impacts of LULCC [3,20].

LULCC analysis using RS and GIS has several applications, including natural resource management, urban planning, and disaster management. In natural resource management, LULCC analysis monitors forest cover changes, wetland degradation, and desertification, prioritizing conservation and restoration actions. In urban planning, LULCC analysis assesses the effects of urbanization on land use and land cover patterns and identifies areas for green infrastructure and sustainable development. In disaster management, LULCC analysis assesses the vulnerability of different areas to natural hazards such as floods, landslides, and wildfires.

III. TECHNIQUES AND APPROACHES FOR LULC CLASSIFICATION

The identification and categorization of different types of land use and land cover within a specific region or area is known as Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) classification. This information is essential for various applications, including environmental monitoring, land use planning, natural resource management, and disaster management. With the advancement of remote sensing technology and image processing techniques, various techniques and approaches for LULC classification have been developed [21-23].

Supervised classification is one of the most commonly used techniques for LULC classification. It involves using a labeled training dataset representing different land cover classes to train a classification algorithm to identify patterns and spectral signatures of each class. The algorithm is then applied to the entire image to classify each pixel into one of the predefined land cover classes. The accuracy of this classification depends on the quality of the training dataset, the choice of classification algorithm, and the quality of the image data.

Another approach for LULC classification is unsupervised classification, which clusters pixels based on their spectral characteristics. The algorithm groups pixels with similar spectral properties into different classes, making it suitable for exploratory analysis. However, the accuracy of unsupervised classification is usually lower than supervised classification.

Machine learning algorithms, such as random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks, have been increasingly applied to LULC classification, particularly for dealing with large datasets, complex landscapes, and multi-spectral images.

LiDAR, synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery are other data sources used for LULC classification. LiDAR data provides high-resolution information about the vertical structure of vegetation, SAR data can penetrate through clouds and

vegetation, and UAV imagery provides high-resolution information about small-scale land cover patterns.

The selection of the appropriate technique and approach for LULC classification depends on several factors, including the study's objectives, data availability and quality, and spatial and temporal resolution requirements. This paper will review and compare the different techniques and approaches for LULC classification, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses and providing insights into their applications in various fields.

A. Manual Classification

The manual classification of land use land cover is the act of visually interpreting and analyzing satellite imagery, aerial photographs, or other remote sensing data to identify and map various land cover and land use categories. This process requires expert knowledge, field observations, and predefined classification rules to classify the land into categories such as forests, grasslands, croplands, urban areas, water bodies, and barren lands.

To start the manual classification process, appropriate satellite imagery or aerial photographs covering the study area are selected and acquired. The imagery must have high spatial and spectral resolution to capture the necessary level of detail for each land use land cover category. After acquiring the imagery, it is pre-processed to remove noise, atmospheric effects, or other artifacts that may affect the classification's accuracy.

Image interpretation is the next step, where the interpreter visually examines the imagery and identifies different land use land cover categories. This process requires expert knowledge and the ability to differentiate between different land cover types based on their spectral, spatial, and temporal characteristics. The interpreter examines the imagery at various scales, from the broad scale of the entire study area to the fine scale of individual land cover features.

Once the different land cover types are identified, the interpreter assigns each feature to a specific land use land cover category using a set of predefined classification rules. These rules may be based on spectral characteristics or spatial characteristics, such as the shape, size, and texture of different land cover features.

Accuracy assessment is the final step in manual classification, which involves comparing the classified map with ground truth data collected in the field or from other sources. This step is essential to ensure the classification's accuracy and to identify any errors or inconsistencies in the classification process. Accuracy assessment may involve statistical measures such as error matrices, kappa coefficients, or overall accuracy assessments.

Manual classification has several advantages over automated classification techniques, including the ability to incorporate expert knowledge and the flexibility to adapt to different study areas and data types. It can also produce

high-quality maps with a high level of detail. However, manual classification also has some limitations, including the potential for subjective interpretation, the time and labor-intensive nature of the process, and difficulty in scaling up to larger study areas.

Manual classification of land use land cover is a valuable technique for mapping and monitoring land cover changes over time. Expert knowledge, field observations, and predefined classification rules are used to identify and map different land use land cover categories. While manual classification has some limitations, it remains an important tool for generating accurate and detailed land use land cover maps.

B. Numerical and Digital Classification

Land use and land cover classification is the process of categorizing the physical and biological characteristics of the earth's surface into distinct classes. This classification is vital for a range of applications, including resource management, land-use planning, and environmental assessment. There are two main methods of land-use and land-cover classification: numerical and digital classification.

Numerical classification, also known as manual classification, involves the identification of land-use and land-cover classes by experts who analyze aerial photographs, satellite imagery, or ground observations. This method is time-consuming, requires skilled personnel, and is subject to human errors. On the other hand, digital classification involves the use of remote sensing data and computer algorithms to automate the classification process. This method is more efficient and accurate than numerical classification because it reduces the time required to identify land-use and land-cover classes and eliminates the human errors associated with visual interpretation.

The digital classification process involves converting remote sensing data into digital numbers that can be analyzed using mathematical algorithms. The algorithms are designed to identify the spectral characteristics of each pixel in the image and assign it to a particular land-use or land-cover class based on pre-defined spectral signatures. The spectral signature of each land-use and land-cover class is unique and is used as a reference for the classification process.

The digital classification method can be further classified into supervised and unsupervised classification. In supervised classification, the analyst provides the computer with a set of training data that contains the spectral signatures of each land-use and land-cover class. The computer uses this information to classify the remaining pixels in the image. In unsupervised classification, the computer automatically identifies the spectral classes present in the image and groups them based on their similarities. The analyst then assigns a land-use and land-cover class to each spectral class based on their characteristics.

The accuracy of land-use and land-cover classification depends on several factors, including the quality of the remote sensing data used, the spectral signature libraries available, and the accuracy of the algorithms used. The quality of remote sensing data can be affected by atmospheric conditions, sun angle, and sensor calibration. The accuracy of the spectral signature libraries depends on the number and diversity of the samples collected from each land-use and land-cover class. The accuracy of the algorithms used depends on the mathematical models used to classify the data.

Land-use and land-cover classification are crucial for various applications, and there are two main methods of classification: numerical and digital classification. While numerical classification involves visual interpretation and is subject to human errors, digital classification involves remote sensing data and computer algorithms and is more efficient and accurate. The accuracy of the classification depends on the quality of the remote sensing data used, the spectral signature libraries available, and the accuracy of the algorithms used.

C. Hybrid Techniques

Hybrid techniques for land use and land cover mapping involve combining both remote sensing data and ground-based data to obtain more precise and reliable information. Remote sensing data refers to the use of sensors on satellites, airplanes, or unmanned aerial vehicles to collect data on the Earth's surface. Ground-based data, on the other hand, includes data gathered through field surveys, interviews, and observations. The integration of these two sources of data can help create accurate and reliable land use and land cover maps.

One of the advantages of using hybrid techniques is that it can enhance the accuracy of land use and land cover mapping. Remote sensing data alone may not provide enough information to distinguish between different land cover types. For instance, it may be challenging to differentiate between grasslands and croplands using satellite imagery. However, ground-based data such as information on crop rotations or field boundaries can provide additional information to help distinguish between different land cover types.

Hybrid techniques can also improve the spatial and temporal resolution of land use and land cover mapping. Remote sensing data has the advantage of covering vast areas, but it may not have a high enough spatial resolution to identify small-scale features such as individual trees or buildings. Ground-based data can provide more detailed information on these features and can also be used to verify the accuracy of remote sensing data.

Moreover, hybrid techniques can monitor changes in land use and land cover over time. Remote sensing data can provide information on land cover changes over large areas, but it may not be able to distinguish between different types of land use changes. Ground-based data can provide more detailed information on these types of changes, which can

help improve the accuracy of land use and land cover maps over time.

Several techniques can be used to combine remote sensing and ground-based data for land use and land cover mapping. One of these is object-based image analysis (OBIA), which involves segmenting satellite imagery into individual objects based on spectral, spatial, and contextual information. Ground-based data such as field surveys or interviews can then be used to classify these objects into different land use and land cover types.

Another technique is participatory mapping, which involves collaborating with local communities to collect ground-based data on land use and land cover. This can include information on land tenure, crop types, and land management practices. This information can be used to validate remote sensing data and improve the accuracy of land use and land cover maps.

Hybrid techniques for land use and land cover mapping can provide more accurate and reliable information than remote sensing or ground-based data alone. By combining these two sources of data, it is possible to enhance the spatial and temporal resolution of land use and land cover maps, monitor changes over time, and verify the accuracy of remote sensing data. These techniques are becoming increasingly crucial in land use and land cover mapping and are likely to become even more important in the future as the demand for accurate and reliable information on land use and land cover continues to grow.

IV. APPLICATION ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) AND MACHINE LEARNING (ML) IN LULC CLASSIFICATION

Land use and land cover (LULC) classification is crucial in various environmental applications, including land-use planning, natural resource management, and ecological conservation. With the help of advanced technology and the availability of large datasets, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms have become widely used in LULC classification. In this essay, we will discuss the application of AI and ML in LULC classification, as well as the benefits and challenges associated with these approaches [24-26].

AI and ML are related fields, with AI referring to machines' ability to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as perception, reasoning, learning, and decision-making. ML, on the other hand, focuses on the development of algorithms that enable machines to learn from data and make predictions or decisions without explicit programming. In LULC classification, ML algorithms can automatically identify and classify different land use and land cover types based on their spectral characteristics.

Supervised classification is one of the most widely used ML algorithms in LULC classification. This approach involves collecting and labeling a set of training samples

with their corresponding land use and land cover types. The algorithm then learns the spectral characteristics of different land use and land cover types using these samples and assigns pixels in the image to the appropriate class based on their similarity to the training samples. Supervised classification algorithms include maximum likelihood, support vector machine, and random forest.

Unsupervised classification is another commonly used ML algorithm in LULC classification. This approach involves the algorithm identifying clusters of pixels in the image that have similar spectral characteristics and assigning them to different land use and land cover types. This approach does not require labeled training samples, but it relies on the assumption that pixels with similar spectral characteristics belong to the same land use or land cover type. Unsupervised classification algorithms include k-means clustering and hierarchical clustering.

The use of AI and ML algorithms in LULC classification offers several advantages. These algorithms can handle large datasets and process images quickly, which is crucial in applications that require up-to-date information, such as disaster management and urban planning. Additionally, they can reduce human error associated with manual classification by providing accurate and consistent results. Finally, they can detect subtle differences in spectral characteristics that may be difficult for human observers to distinguish, improving the accuracy of classification results.

Despite the advantages of AI and ML in LULC classification, there are several challenges associated with these approaches. The availability and quality of training data is one of the primary challenges. The accuracy of classification results in supervised classification depends on the quality and representativeness of the training samples. In unsupervised classification, the accuracy of classification results depends on the number of clusters and the criteria used to determine the optimal number of clusters. Therefore, it is essential to collect sufficient and representative training data to ensure accurate classification results.

The complexity of ML algorithms is another challenge that can make it difficult to interpret classification results. While AI and ML algorithms can provide accurate classification results, they often lack transparency, making it difficult to understand how they arrive at their decisions. This can be a significant challenge in applications that require a high level of transparency, such as legal or regulatory decisions.

AI and ML algorithms have become essential tools in LULC classification. They can handle large datasets, reduce human error, and detect subtle differences in spectral characteristics, improving the accuracy of classification results. However, the accuracy of classification results depends on the quality and representativeness of the training data, and the complexity of ML algorithms can make it difficult to interpret classification results. Therefore, it is crucial to collect sufficient and representative training data

and carefully evaluate the accuracy and transparency of classification results.

V. ENVIRONMENT AND RISK EVALUATION

Land use and land cover have significant influence on the environment and the level of risks associated with human activities. Thus, evaluating the environment and risks related to land use and land cover is crucial in identifying potential threats to environmental sustainability and human wellbeing. This assessment is essential to comprehend how land use changes impact ecosystem services, biodiversity, and human health and welfare.

Assessing land use and land cover involves examining the physical, chemical, and biological aspects of the environment, including air, water, soil, and vegetation quality. It also involves analyzing human activities that may affect these components, such as agriculture, urbanization, and mining. Through an understanding of the current state of these components and their relationship with human activities, potential risks to the environment and human populations can be identified [27,28].

The loss of biodiversity is one of the key environmental risks associated with land use and land cover. Activities like deforestation and urbanization can lead to habitat destruction, fragmentation, and loss of biodiversity. This loss of biodiversity can have significant ecological and economic impacts, such as the loss of essential ecosystem services like pollination, pest control, and nutrient cycling. Therefore, assessing land use and land cover should take into account the potential impact of human activities on biodiversity and develop measures to mitigate it.

Another environmental risk associated with land use and land cover is the degradation of soil quality. Activities like intensive agriculture and mining can cause soil erosion, compaction, and depletion of soil nutrients. This can have significant impacts on agricultural productivity, water quality, and biodiversity. Thus, assessing land use and land cover should consider the potential impact of human activities on soil quality and develop measures to mitigate it.

Human activities related to land use and land cover can also pose risks to human health and welfare. For instance, exposure to air pollution from industrial activities or transportation can result in respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Similarly, exposure to contaminated water or soil can cause severe health risks like infectious diseases, cancer, and neurological disorders. Thus, assessing land use and land cover should also consider the potential impact of human activities on human health and welfare and develop measures to mitigate it.

Evaluating land use and land cover is crucial in understanding the potential environmental and human risks related to human activities. Through identifying potential risks and developing measures to mitigate them, environmental sustainability can be promoted, and the wellbeing of human populations can be protected. To ensure

sustainable land management practices, environmental and risk evaluation is a crucial aspect of land management. This process involves using remote sensing (RS) and geographic information system (GIS) to analyze land use and land cover changes and assess their impacts on the environment. RS and GIS are the primary tools for assessing the environment and the risks associated with land use activities [1-3,22-25].

Remote sensing utilizes satellites or aircraft to capture images of the earth's surface, providing a comprehensive view of the land and detecting land use and land cover changes. GIS is a computer-based tool that integrates and analyzes spatial data. Together, RS and GIS are powerful tools for analyzing land use and land cover changes and assessing their impacts on the environment.

One of the main applications of RS and GIS in environmental and risk evaluation is the mapping of land use and land cover changes. This process provides valuable information on the distribution and extent of different land uses and land covers, such as urban areas, forests, wetlands, and agricultural land. This information is used to identify areas that have undergone changes in land use and land cover and monitor the impacts of these changes on the environment.

Another application of RS and GIS is analyzing the impacts of land use and land cover changes on the environment. These changes can affect the environment in various ways, such as changes in the hydrological cycle, soil erosion, and loss of biodiversity. RS and GIS can analyze these impacts and identify areas that are at risk of environmental degradation.

RS and GIS are also used to identify areas at risk of natural disasters, such as floods and landslides. Factors such as slope, soil type, and rainfall are analyzed to identify areas susceptible to these hazards. This information is then used to develop strategies for mitigating the risks associated with these natural disasters.

RS and GIS are valuable tools for environmental and risk evaluation using land use and land cover analysis. They provide detailed information on land use and land cover changes and their impacts on the environment, enabling effective land management and protection of the environment. The use of RS and GIS in environmental and risk evaluation is essential for sustainable land management practices.

VI. STAGES OF PROCESS LULC CLASSIFICATION

Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) classification is a process that involves categorizing the Earth's surface into various land use and land cover classes based on the interpretation of remotely sensed images. It is essential in understanding natural resource dynamics and environmental changes over time. The LULC classification process consists of several stages that are crucial in achieving the accuracy and precision of the final output.

➤ *Data Acquisition*

The first stage in the LULC classification process is data acquisition. The data used in this process are typically obtained from remote sensing platforms like satellites, aerial photography, or LiDAR data. The data must be of high quality and resolution to ensure the accuracy of the classification. The spatial resolution should be suitable for the study area and the desired level of detail. Additionally, the data should cover the study area comprehensively and be free from any distortions or errors that could affect the classification accuracy.

➤ *Image Preprocessing*

After data acquisition, the next stage is image preprocessing. The acquired data needs to undergo several steps such as radiometric and geometric corrections, image enhancement, and filtering before it can be used for classification. Radiometric correction is used to remove atmospheric effects on the image, while geometric correction is used to align the image to the correct position on the Earth's surface. Image enhancement and filtering are used to improve the image quality and reduce noise.

➤ *Image Segmentation*

The third stage is image segmentation. It involves dividing the image into smaller segments based on the characteristics of the image, such as texture, color, and shape. The goal of segmentation is to identify the homogenous regions within the image that can be classified into a single LULC class. Segmentation can be done using various algorithms like region-growing, watershed, and graph-based algorithms.

➤ *Feature Extraction*

The feature extraction stage follows the image segmentation stage. This stage involves extracting features from the segmented image that can be used to classify the different land cover and land use classes. The features can be spectral, spatial, or contextual. Spectral features include the reflectance values of the different bands in the image, while spatial features include the size, shape, and texture of the segmented regions. Contextual features consider the relationships between adjacent regions in the image.

➤ *Classification*

After feature extraction, the next stage is classification. This stage involves assigning each segmented region in the image to a specific LULC class based on the extracted features. Classification can be supervised or unsupervised. In supervised classification, training samples are selected from the image, and a classification algorithm is trained to recognize the different LULC classes based on these samples. In unsupervised classification, the algorithm clusters the image segments into different LULC classes based on the similarity of their features.

➤ *Accuracy Assessment*

Accuracy assessment is the next stage in the LULC classification process. This stage involves determining the accuracy of the LULC classification results. This is done by comparing the classified image with ground truth data

obtained through field surveys or other reliable sources. The accuracy of the classification can be quantified using various measures, such as overall accuracy, producer's accuracy, and user's accuracy.

➤ *Post-Classification Processing*

The final stage is post-classification processing. This stage involves refining the classification results by removing misclassified pixels or merging adjacent regions with similar characteristics. This stage is crucial in improving the accuracy of the classification results and producing a final LULC map that accurately represents the Earth's surface.

The LULC classification process is a crucial step in understanding natural resource dynamics and environmental changes over time. Each stage of the process is essential in achieving an accurate and precise classification result. By following these stages, we can gain a better understanding of the Earth's surface and make informed decisions in sustainable development planning.

VII. FACTORS AFFECTING THE LULC CLASSIFICATION

The following are the various factors that can impact the accuracy and reliability of land use and land cover (LULC) classification. To ensure precise and dependable LULC classification, the following factors should be considered and mitigated:

➤ *Spatial and Temporal Resolution of Satellite Images:*

The spatial and temporal resolution of satellite images plays a significant role in LULC classification accuracy. Low spatial resolution images can lead to mixed pixels and misclassification of land cover types. Similarly, low temporal resolution can affect tracking seasonal or annual changes in land use. To mitigate this, higher resolution images should be acquired, and multi-temporal imagery should be utilized.

The accuracy of LULC classification is heavily influenced by spatial resolution, as it determines the level of detail that can be captured in an image. Higher spatial resolution can capture more detail, allowing for better differentiation between land cover types. For example, an image with a spatial resolution of 1 meter can differentiate between tree species, whereas an image with a resolution of 30 meters cannot. Additionally, higher spatial resolution images can reduce mixed pixels, where a single pixel contains multiple land cover types, making classification challenging.

Temporal resolution is also important for LULC classification because it captures changes in land use/land cover over time. For instance, comparing a summer image of a forested area with a winter image can reveal changes such as land clearance for agriculture. Higher temporal resolution images can capture seasonal changes in land use/land cover, such as crop changes or water body fluctuations due to seasonal rainfall. The classification

accuracy can be improved by detecting and recording these changes.

However, there is a trade-off between spatial and temporal resolution. High spatial resolution images often have low temporal resolution, as it takes longer to collect and process data from high-resolution sensors. Conversely, high temporal resolution images may have lower spatial resolution, as sensors with higher temporal resolution cover larger areas at a lower level of detail.

The choice of satellite image should be based on specific LULC classification objectives, as well as the availability and cost of different types of satellite data. A higher spatial resolution image might be more appropriate if the goal is to accurately classify different types of land cover. In contrast, a higher temporal resolution image might be more appropriate for tracking changes in land use/land cover over time.

➤ *Image Pre-Processing:*

Radiometric calibration, atmospheric correction, and geometric correction are crucial pre-processing steps that can affect the accuracy of LULC classification. Any errors in these steps can lead to incorrect classification results. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that these steps are accurately performed.

➤ *Spectral Bands used:*

The choice of spectral bands used for LULC classification significantly impacts classification accuracy. Selecting appropriate spectral bands that can differentiate between different land cover types is vital for precise classification.

➤ *Training Data Selection:*

The accuracy of LULC classification depends on the quality and quantity of the training data used. Representative training data covering all the land cover types present is crucial for accurate classification. Land use classification involves categorizing different land cover types based on their usage, and it plays a critical role in urban planning, natural resource management, and environmental monitoring. To achieve accurate land use classification, the quality of the training data used to train the models is vital. The selection of training data can affect land use classification in various ways. For instance, biased training data can negatively impact the accuracy of the classification model by favoring one or more land use types. Inadequate training data that fails to represent the variety of land cover types present in the study area may compromise the model's accuracy. The quality of training data is also essential, as errors or poor labeling can lead to inaccurate results. Consistency over time is crucial when training the model, and the spatial distribution of the training data should be evenly distributed to represent the area's land use types accurately. It is crucial to have training data that is representative, sufficient, high quality, consistent over time, and spatially distributed to achieve reliable land use classification results.

By considering and mitigating these factors, the accuracy and reliability of LULC classification can be significantly improved.

VIII. ACCURACY ASSESSMENT

To ensure the reliability of a land use land cover (LULC) classification map, it is crucial to assess its accuracy [22-25]. This process involves comparing the classification map to a reference dataset containing the actual land use land cover types in the study area. The reference dataset can be obtained through fieldwork or high-resolution satellite imagery. The accuracy of the classification map is usually expressed as an overall accuracy, user's accuracy, and producer's accuracy for each land use land cover class.

The overall accuracy is calculated as the percentage of correctly classified pixels in the map, while the user's and producer's accuracy are calculated as the percentage of correctly classified pixels for a specific land use land cover class and the percentage of pixels correctly classified as a specific land use land cover class, respectively. To perform accuracy assessment, a sample of pixels is randomly selected from the classification map and compared to the reference dataset using statistical methods such as confusion matrix analysis, kappa coefficient, and overall accuracy.

The accuracy of the LULC classification is affected by various factors such as the quality of the remotely sensed data, accuracy of the reference dataset, and classification algorithm used. It is important to select an appropriate classification algorithm that suits the study area and the level of detail required. Accuracy assessment should also be performed regularly to ensure that the classification map remains reliable, especially if there are changes in land use land cover types in the study area.

In the field of remote sensing, assessing the accuracy of land use classification is essential to evaluate the performance of classification algorithms and estimate the reliability of the resulting land use map. A widely used tool in accuracy assessment is the confusion matrix, which summarizes the classification results in a tabular format. This matrix compares the actual land use classes on the ground (reference data) to the classified land use classes obtained from remote sensing data, with four cells representing true positive (TP), false positive (FP), true negative (TN), and false negative (FN) classifications.

TP represents the number of pixels correctly classified into the class of interest, while FP represents the number of pixels incorrectly classified into the class of interest. TN represents the number of pixels correctly classified into classes other than the class of interest, and FN represents the number of pixels incorrectly classified as classes other than the class of interest.

Various statistical metrics can be calculated from the confusion matrix to evaluate the accuracy of land use classification. Overall accuracy, user's accuracy, producer's

accuracy, and Kappa coefficient are some of the commonly used metrics.

Overall accuracy represents the percentage of correctly classified pixels out of the total number of pixels in the reference data. User's accuracy represents the percentage of correctly classified pixels in a particular class out of the total number of pixels classified as that class. Producer's accuracy represents the percentage of correctly classified pixels in a particular class out of the total number of pixels in the reference data that belong to that class.

Kappa coefficient is a statistical measure of agreement between the classification results and the reference data, accounting for the agreement that would occur by chance. Kappa coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 represents no agreement, and 1 represents perfect agreement.

Confusion matrix analysis is a fundamental tool in accuracy assessment of land use classification, allowing for the evaluation of classification algorithm performance, identification of strengths and weaknesses in classification, and estimation of map reliability. The statistical metrics obtained from the confusion matrix provide quantitative measures of accuracy that are essential in various applications, including environmental monitoring, land management, and urban planning.

Accuracy assessment is a crucial step in the LULC classification process, as it ensures the reliability of the resulting map [24-27]. By comparing the classification map to a reference dataset and calculating various measures of accuracy, it is possible to evaluate the quality of the classification and make informed decisions based on the resulting map.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are effective tools for detecting and assessing accuracy of Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) changes. This paper has reviewed various studies demonstrating the capabilities of RS and GIS in monitoring LULC changes, assessing their accuracy, and analyzing the drivers behind them. These studies have proven that RS and GIS provide precise and timely information on LULC changes.

RS and GIS have advantages in LULC monitoring, such as obtaining spatially explicit information over large areas. With high-resolution imagery, RS can identify and map LULC changes at various scales while GIS can integrate RS data with other sources like socioeconomic data to analyze LULC change drivers. Additionally, RS and GIS provide a reliable and cost-effective way to assess the accuracy of LULC classifications, improving the quality of LULC maps.

Nevertheless, there are some challenges in LULC monitoring using RS and GIS. Obtaining accurate ground truth data for validation purposes, especially in remote areas,

is one of the main challenges. Additionally, skilled personnel are needed to analyze and interpret RS and GIS data, which can be expensive and time-consuming.

In conclusion, RS and GIS are valuable tools for LULC monitoring and accuracy assessment, despite some challenges. These tools can provide precise information on LULC changes, which can help inform policy decisions and land use planning. Therefore, it is recommended that further research is conducted to explore the potential of RS and GIS in LULC monitoring and accuracy assessment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Attri, P., Chaudhry, S., & Sharma, S. (2015). Remote sensing & GIS based approaches for LULC change detection—A review. *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology*, 5(5), 3126-3137.
- [2] Alshari, E. A., & Gawali, B. W. (2021). Development of classification system for LULC using remote sensing and GIS. *Global transitions proceedings*, 2(1), 8-17.
- [3] Gidado, K. A., Kamarudin, M. K. A., Firdaus, N. A., Nalado, A. M., Saudi, A. S. M., Saad, M. H. M., & Ibrahim, S. (2018). Analysis of spatiotemporal land use and land cover changes using remote sensing and GIS: a review. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(4.34), 159-162.
- [4] Liu, P., Jia, S., Han, R., Liu, Y., Lu, X., & Zhang, H. (2020). RS and GIS supported urban LULC and UHI change simulation and assessment. *Journal of Sensors*, 2020, 1-17.
- [5] Ahmed, R., Ahmad, S. T., Wani, G. F., Ahmed, P., Mir, A. A., & Singh, A. (2022). Analysis of landuse and landcover changes in Kashmir valley, India—a review. *GeoJournal*, 87(5), 4391-4403.
- [6] Yasir, M., Hui, S., Binghu, H., & Rahman, S. U. (2020). Coastline extraction and land use change analysis using remote sensing (RS) and geographic information system (GIS) technology—A review of the literature. *Reviews on environmental health*, 35(4), 453-460.
- [7] Nath, B., Niu, Z., & Singh, R. P. (2018). Land Use and Land Cover changes, and environment and risk evaluation of Dujiangyan city (SW China) using remote sensing and GIS techniques. *Sustainability*, 10(12), 4631.
- [8] Twisa, S., & Buchroithner, M. F. (2019). Land-use and land-cover (LULC) change detection in Wami River Basin, Tanzania. *Land*, 8(9), 136.
- [9] Rane, N. L., & Jayaraj, G. K. (2022). Comparison of multi-influence factor, weight of evidence and frequency ratio techniques to evaluate groundwater potential zones of basaltic aquifer systems. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(2), 2315-2344. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01535-5>
- [10] Rane, N. L., & Attarde, P. M. (2016). Application of value engineering in commercial building projects. *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology*, 6(3), 286-291.

- [11] Rane, N., & Jayaraj, G. K. (2021). Stratigraphic modeling and hydraulic characterization of a typical basaltic aquifer system in the Kadva river basin, Nashik, India. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 7, 293-306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-01008-0>
- [12] Rane, N., & Jayaraj, G. K. (2021). Evaluation of multiwell pumping aquifer tests in unconfined aquifer system by Neuman (1975) method with numerical modeling. In *Groundwater resources development and planning in the semi-arid region* (pp. 93-106). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-68124-1_5
- [13] Kaliraj, S., Chandrasekar, N., Ramachandran, K. K., Srinivas, Y., & Saravanan, S. (2017). Coastal landuse and land cover change and transformations of Kanyakumari coast, India using remote sensing and GIS. *The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science*, 20(2), 169-185.
- [14] Olokeogun, O. S., Iyiola, K., & Iyiola, O. F. (2014). Application of remote sensing and GIS in land use/land cover mapping and change detection in Shasha forest reserve, Nigeria. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 40(8), 613-616.
- [15] Chughtai, A. H., Abbasi, H., & Karas, I. R. (2021). A review on change detection method and accuracy assessment for land use land cover. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 22, 100482.
- [16] Rane, N. L., (2016). Application of value engineering techniques in building construction projects. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Technology*, 5(7).
- [17] Rane, N., Lopes, S., Raval, A., Rumaio, D., & Thakur, M. P. (2017). Study of effects of labour productivity on construction projects. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences and Research Technology*, 6(6), 15-20.
- [18] Hussain, S., Mubeen, M., & Karuppannan, S. (2022). Land use and land cover (LULC) change analysis using TM, ETM+ and OLI Landsat images in district of Okara, Punjab, Pakistan. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts a/b/c*, 126, 103117.
- [19] Natarajan, K., Latva-Käyrä, P., Zyadin, A., & Pelkonen, P. (2016). New methodological approach for biomass resource assessment in India using GIS application and land use/land cover (LULC) maps. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 63, 256-268.
- [20] Reis, S. (2008). Analyzing land use/land cover changes using remote sensing and GIS in Rize, North-East Turkey. *Sensors*, 8(10), 6188-6202.
- [21] Paudel, B., Zhang, Y. L., Li, S. C., Liu, L. S., Wu, X., & Khanal, N. R. (2016). Review of studies on land use and land cover change in Nepal. *Journal of Mountain Science*, 13, 643-660.
- [22] Rane, N. L., Anand, A., Deepak K., (2023). Evaluating the Selection Criteria of Formwork System (FS) for RCC Building Construction. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 197-205. Crossref, <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V71I3P220>
- [23] Achari, A., Rane, N. L., Gangar B., (2023). Framework Towards Achieving Sustainable Strategies for Water Usage and Wastage in Building Construction. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 385-394. Crossref, <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V71I3P241>
- [24] Rwanga, S. S., & Ndambuki, J. M. (2017). Accuracy assessment of land use/land cover classification using remote sensing and GIS. *International Journal of Geosciences*, 8(04), 611.
- [25] Lu, D., Li, G., Valladares, G. S., & Batistella, M. (2004). Mapping soil erosion risk in Rondonia, Brazilian Amazonia: using RUSLE, remote sensing and GIS. *Land degradation & development*, 15(5), 499-512.
- [26] Vivekananda, G. N., Swathi, R., & Sujith, A. V. L. N. (2021). Multi-temporal image analysis for LULC classification and change detection. *European journal of remote sensing*, 54(sup2), 189-199.
- [27] Ahmad, F., Goparaju, L., & Qayum, A. (2017). LULC analysis of urban spaces using Markov chain predictive model at Ranchi in India. *Spatial Information Research*, 25(3), 351-359.
- [28] Roy, P. S., & Roy, A. (2010). Land use and land cover change in India: A remote sensing & GIS perspective. *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, 90(4), 489-502.